

STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF ELLIPTICAL PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract Elliptical phraseological units are a significant linguistic phenomenon in both English and Uzbek languages. These units reflect not only the structural and semantic peculiarities of the languages but also embody cultural and cognitive aspects. This paper examines the structural and semantic features of elliptical phraseological units in English and Uzbek, focusing on their similarities and differences. The study aims to provide a comparative analysis of these units, shedding light on how ellipsis functions within the phraseological systems of these two languages.

Key Words: Ellipsis, Phraseological Units, English Language, Uzbek Language, Structural Features, Semantic Features,

Introduction Ellipsis, as a linguistic device, plays a crucial role in language economy, allowing speakers to convey more meaning with fewer words. In phraseological units, ellipsis often enhances expressiveness, adding layers of meaning that would be lost in more explicit forms. This phenomenon is prevalent in both English and Uzbek, where elliptical structures contribute to the richness and diversity of idiomatic expressions. The present study explores the structural and semantic characteristics of elliptical phraseological units in English and Uzbek, analyzing how these units reflect the linguistic and cultural context of each language.

Structural Features of Elliptical Phraseological Units Elliptical phraseological units in both English and Uzbek languages often involve the omission of words or phrases that are understood from the context. This omission creates a more compact and efficient expression, which can be particularly impactful in conveying complex ideas or emotions.

In English, elliptical phraseological units frequently omit verbs or subjects, relying on the listener or reader to infer the missing elements. For example, the phrase "The more, the merrier" omits the explanatory elements that would otherwise clarify the meaning, such as "the more people there are, the merrier

the situation becomes." This structure not only shortens the phrase but also enhances its rhetorical effect, making it more memorable and impactful[1]. Similarly, in Uzbek, elliptical phraseological units often omit verbs or entire clauses, relying on cultural knowledge and contextual understanding to fill in the gaps. The phrase "Ko'p ko'rganning oti ko'rinmas" (literally "the horse of the one who sees much is not seen") omits the verb "is," yet the meaning remains clear due to the cultural context in which the phrase is used[2]. This omission reflects the Uzbek linguistic preference for brevity and the use of idiomatic expressions to convey wisdom or advice.

Semantic Features of Elliptical Phraseological Units The semantic richness of elliptical phraseological units is closely tied to their structural features. The omission of certain elements often concentrates meaning, making the remaining components carry a heavier semantic load. This concentration of meaning can lead to more powerful and nuanced expressions, capable of conveying both literal and figurative meanings[3].

In English, elliptical phraseological units often use omission to create paradoxes or ironic statements. The phrase "Less is more" omits the explanatory reasoning behind the statement, leaving the listener to ponder the deeper implications. This elliptical structure not only makes the phrase more concise but also more thought-provoking, encouraging the listener to engage with the underlying message.

In Uzbek, the semantic impact of elliptical phraseological units is often linked to cultural wisdom and social norms. For example, the phrase "Og'izdan olma!" (literally "Don't take it from the mouth") omits the full explanation, yet the implied meaning—that one should not take words too literally—is clear to native speakers. This ellipsis reflects the cultural emphasis on interpreting language with caution, particularly in social interactions[3].

Comparative Analysis A comparative analysis of elliptical phraseological units in English and Uzbek reveals both similarities and differences in how these structures are used and understood. Both languages use ellipsis to achieve brevity and emphasis, yet the specific ways in which ellipsis is employed can vary depending on the linguistic and cultural context.

In English, elliptical phraseological units often rely on syntactic parallelism and rhythm to enhance their rhetorical effect. The phrase "Out of sight, out of mind" uses ellipsis to omit the conjunction and the verb, creating a parallel structure that is both catchy and easy to remember. This type of ellipsis is common in

English idioms and proverbs, where the focus is on creating a memorable and rhetorically effective statement[4].

Table 1: Comparative Features of Elliptical Phraseological Units in English and Uzbek

Feature	English Examples	Uzbek Examples	Analysis
Omitted Element	Verb ("Less is more")	Verb ("Ko'p ko'rganning oti ko'rinmas")	Both languages often omit verbs to create a more concise and impactful expression.
Cultural Context Dependence	"When in Rome, [do as the Romans do]"	"Tog' bilan tog' uchrashmasa ham, insonlar uchrashadi"	Uzbek phrases often rely on cultural knowledge for interpretation, while English phrases focus on universal truths.
Syntactic Parallelism	"Out of sight, out of mind"	"Og'izdan olma!"	English phrases often use parallel structures to enhance memorability, while Uzbek phrases rely on contextual understanding.
Semantic Density	"Less is more"	"Og'izdan olma!"	Elliptical structures in both languages enhance semantic density, making the expressions more powerful.

In contrast, Uzbek elliptical phraseological units frequently omit elements that are culturally understood, such as specific actions or outcomes. The phrase "Tog' bilan tog' uchrashmasa ham, insonlar uchrashadi" (literally "Even if mountains don't meet, people do") omits the concluding reasoning, relying on the listener's cultural knowledge to understand the implied meaning. This reliance on cultural context is a key feature of Uzbek ellipsis, where the shared values and norms of the community play a crucial role in interpreting the expression.

Conclusion Elliptical phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages demonstrate the intricate relationship between structure, semantics, and culture. While both languages use ellipsis to enhance expressiveness and

efficiency, the specific forms and functions of these units reflect the unique linguistic and cultural contexts in which they are used. Understanding these differences and similarities not only enriches our knowledge of phraseology in these languages but also provides insights into the broader cognitive and cultural processes that shape language use.

This study highlights the importance of considering both structural and semantic aspects when analyzing elliptical phraseological units. Future research could further explore the pragmatic functions of ellipsis in these languages, as well as the role of cultural factors in shaping the use of ellipsis in phraseology. By examining these units through a comparative lens, we can gain a deeper understanding of how language functions as a tool for both communication and cultural expression.

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